

Correlation between the Molecular Structure of the Chelating Agents and the Properties of Ferric Chelates

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The properties of ferric chelates of hydroxy ketones and ketoximes have been correlated with molecular structure of reagents, by taking into consideration the optimum pH range for the formation of chelates, the wavelength of maximum absorbance of the chelates, molecular extinction coefficients at λ_{maxima} , stability constants, the standard free energies of formation, the sensitivity of reagents and optimum concentration of ferric ions which can be measured by these reagents. The complexes are formed by the replacement of hydroxyl hydrogen atom by ferric atom, which in turn is coordinated to carbonyl oxygen atom or the oxime nitrogen atom.

A study of the chelates of ferric ions with several orthohydroxy ketones and ketoximes was undertaken by us to understand

- (1) the properties of the iron chelates of substituted hydroxy propiophenones and butyrophenones and their oximes;
- (2) to study the suitability of the above mentioned ligands as reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of iron; and
- (3) to correlate the molecular structure of the ligand with the property of chelate formed and with their colour reaction of ferric ions.

A systematic study of the formation of ferric complexes of 2, 4 dihydroxy acetophenone (DHA), 2, 4 dihydroxy propiophenone (DHP), 2, 4 dihydroxy butyrophenone (DHB), 2, 4 dihydroxy propiophenone oxime (DHPOX), 2, 4 dihydroxy butyrophenone oxime (DHBOX), orthohydroxypropiophenone oxime (OHPOX), orthohydroxybutyrophenone oxime (OHBOX) has been undertaken with the above mentioned view points. Spectrophotometric methods were followed for the study and the scheme for investigation of new reagent suggested by Yoe¹ was followed.

A study of the composition of the chelates by (1) Job's method of continuous variation², (2) mole ratio method³, (3) slope ratio method⁴, and (4) Bent and French method⁵ suggested that all the complexes formed have a 1:1 composition. A summary of the important characteristics of the complexes is given in table 1. The stability constants were calculated from the data obtained in the method of continuous variation and the mole ratio method.

1. J. H. Yoe, *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, **36**, 1253.
2. P. Job, *Ann.*, 1928, **9**, 113; 1936, **16**, 97.
3. J. H. Yoe and A. L. Jones, *Industr. Engg. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
4. A. E. Harvey and D. L. Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4448.
5. H. E. Bent and D. L. French, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1195.

TABLE I

Characteristics of the ferric complexes investigated

Name of the complex	Optimum pH range	Selected pH for the study	Wave length of maximum absorbance m μ	Molecular Extinction coefficient.	Stability constant $\mu=0.1M$ NaClO ₄	Sensitivity Sandell Scale $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$	Optimum concentration of Fe ⁺⁺⁺ ions in p.p.m.	Standard free energy of formation k cal.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Ferric-2, 4-dihydroxy acetophenone	2.9-3.0	2.95	470	21.04 $\times 10^2$ (at 470 m μ)	0.802 $\times 10^3$	0.084	5.3-18.7	-4.000
Ferric-2, 4-dihydroxy propiophenone	2.9-3.0	2.95	470	13.78 $\times 10^2$ (at 470 m μ)	1.29 $\times 10^3$	0.126	8.1-28.5	-4.285
Ferric-2, 4-dihydroxy butyrophenone	2.9-3.0	2.95	470	12.37 $\times 10^2$ (at 470 m μ)	0.68 $\times 10^3$	0.131	9.0-31.7	-3.903
Ferric-2,4 dihydroxy propiophenone oxime	2.6-2.8	2.7	510	21.74 $\times 10^2$ (at 510 m μ)	1.43 $\times 10^3$	0.056	5.1-18.0	-4.550
Ferric-2, 4-dihydroxy butyrophenone oxime	2.6-2.8	2.7	510	15.00 $\times 10^2$ (at 510 m μ)	1.1 $\times 10^3$	0.074	7.4-26.1	-4.188
Ferric-ortho-hydroxy propiophenone oxime	2.85-2.95	2.9	General absorption	23.02 $\times 10^2$ (at 510 m μ)	1.56 $\times 10^3$	0.050	4.9-17.0	-4.399
Ferric-ortho-hydroxy butyrophenone oxime	2.85-2.95	2.9	-do-	20.10 $\times 10^2$ (at 510 m μ)	1.13 $\times 10^3$	0.056	5.6-19.5	-4.205

2,4 dihydroxyacetophenone(I), 2,4 dihydroxypropiophenone (II) and 2,4 dihydroxybutyrophenone (III) have a similar structure. except for the alkyl group in the side chain.

All the three compounds form coloured chelates with ferric ions which are reddish violet between pH 2.0 and 3.0, and reddish brown above pH 3.0, the former being stable. The reddish violet complexes formed in the pH range 2.0 and 3.0 show a maximum absorbance at 470 m μ , the optimum pH range is 2.9—3.0. With the increase in the number of carbon atoms in the side chain, the molar absorptivity and sensitivity are found to decrease and a corresponding change is brought about in the optimum concentration range.

But with the increase in the number of the carbon atoms in the side chain, the selectivity increases. This is evident from table II.

TABLE II

*Tolerance limits of diverse ions.**Fe⁺⁺⁺ 0.0002 M (11.2 p.p.m.) pH 2.95.**Reagent 0.006 M.*

	DHA	DHP	DHB
Cr ⁺⁺⁺	500	500	1000
Co ⁺⁺	500	500	1000
Cu ⁺⁺	5	10	50
Ni ⁺⁺	500	1000	1000
Ag ⁺	250	500	1000
UO ₂ ⁺⁺	500	1000	1000
HCO ₃ ⁻	5	10	20
Br ⁻	500	500	750
I ⁻	100	100	250

These ketones possess an acidic OH group in an ortho position to a coordinating keto group. Therefore these compounds may form six membered chelate rings in which the ferric atom replaces the hydroxyl hydrogen atom, and is in turn coordinated to the carbonyl oxygen atom, the probable structure of the complex being

where R = CH₃, C₂H₅ or C₃H₇

2, 4 dihydroxypropiophenone oxime (IV) and 2, 4 dihydroxybutyrophenone oxime (V) have been synthesised from the corresponding ketones (II) and (III). The ferric complexes are purple between pH 2.0 and 3.0 and red above pH 3.0, the former being stable. A comparison of the ferric complexes of ketoximes with those of ketones shows that the conversion of the ketone group into the ketoxime group induces a shift in the optimum pH (from 2.9—3.0 to 2.6—2.8) and a hypsochromic effect (from 470 mμ to 510 mμ).

Orthohydroxypropiophenone oxime (VI) and orthohydroxybutyrophenone oxime (VII) are similar substances having the same functional group as compounds (IV) and

(V) but, in this case, the position No. 4 is occupied by an H atom instead of an OH group.

This change in molecular structure decreases the solubility of the reagent in water, or a aqueous alcohol, and brings about a change in the spectral characteristics of the complex marked by a general absorption of light. The ferric complexes of these ligands are red between pH 2.0 and 3.0 and brown above pH 3.0, the former being stable.

The effect of the increase of the number of carbon atoms in the side chain in hydroxyketoximes is similar to the effect observed in the homologous series of 2,4 dihydroxyketones. The optimum pH range and the spectral characteristics are similar in the ferric complexes formed by the members of the same series, but the lengthening of the side chain induces a decrease in the extinction coefficient and the sensitivity. However, the selectivity is enhanced by the lengthening of side chain as is evident from table III.

TABLE III

Tolerance limits of diverse ions (ppm)

Fe^{+++} 0.0002 M (11.2 $p.p.m.$)

Reagent 0.006 M .

	DHPOX	DHBOX	OHPOX	OHBOX
pH	2.7	2.7	2.9	2.9
Cr^{+++}	500	500	500	500
Co^{++}	500	750	500	500
Cu^{++}	10	15	20	25
Pb^{++}	500	500	500	750
Ni^{++}	500	1000	500	750
Ag^+	500	500	1000	1000
HCO_3^-	10	15	10	10
Br^-	500	750	500	750
I^-	100	150	150	250

In dihydroxyketones, as well as in monohydroxy or dihydroxyketoximes, the substitution of butyl group in the place of propyl group decreases the stability constants.

The oximes are less selective than the corresponding ketones which might be due to the lower reactivity of the functional orthohydroxyketo group as compared with the orthohydroxyketoxime group.

The orthohydroxy ketoximes form a six membered chelate ring through coordination of oxime Nitrogen atom, the probable structure of the complex being.

where $R' = \text{H}$ or OH

$R = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$ or C_3H_7

To confirm that the chelation has occurred through the displacement of a proton from the OH group, the following experiment was carried out. The $p\text{H}$ of 50 ml. of 0.01 M ferric nitrate and 5 ml. of 0.1 M reagent were initially measured. When these solutions were mixed, the $p\text{H}$ was found to decrease, indicating an increase in the H^+ ion concentration of the mixture, which is possible due to the displacement of the hydrogen of the acidic OH group by the ferric ion. The increase in $p\text{H}$ due to complex formation is listed in table IV.

TABLE IV

Change in pH value on mixing reactants.

$p\text{H}$ -ferric Nitrate 0.01 M	Reagent	$p\text{H}$ Reagent 0.1 M	$p\text{H}$ mixture
1.9	2, 4 dihydroxy acetophenone	3.6	1.70
1.9	2, 4 dihydroxy propiophenone	3.7	1.75
1.9	2,4 dihydroxy butyrophenone	3.8	1.80
1.9	2,4 dihydroxy propiophenone	3.6	1.65
1.9	2,4 dihydroxy butyrophenone oxime	3.7	1.70
1.9	<i>O</i> -hydroxy propiophenone oxime	3.2	1.40
1.9	orthohydroxy butyrophenone oxime	3.3	1.50

The reaction for the formation of the complexes of compounds I, II, and III can be represented by

The corresponding reaction of the formation of complexes of the compounds IV to VII can be written as

where R = C₂H₅ or C₃H₇

R' = H or OH

The authors thank Dr. B. K. Vaidya for his kind interest and the Ministry of Education, Government of India, for the award of a research training scholarship to Miss. M. H. Gandhi.

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Received, July 14, 1967.